

Measuring Export Performance with Accounting-Based Financial Indicators: A Proposed Integrated Conceptual Model

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to propose an integrated measurement model based on accounting-based financial indicators, moving beyond one-dimensional approaches based solely on sales volume in measuring export performance. The study is a conceptual model development research that combines marketing and accounting literature. In this context, export performance is examined within the framework of three financial dimensions: sales-based performance, profitability-based performance, and cash flow-based performance. A composite performance index based on Z-score standardization is proposed to make indicators with different units of measurement comparable. The calculation process of the proposed model is numerically demonstrated using a hypothetical dataset. The findings reveal that evaluating export performance solely based on sales volume can be misleading, and that considering profitability and cash flow dimensions together provides a more realistic and sustainable performance assessment. The study provides a conceptual and methodological contribution to the literature by offering an interdisciplinary measurement framework that allows for the correlation of export performance with firm value.

Keywords: Export performance, financial performance, composite performance index, accounting-based performance measurement

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This study is derived from the PhD dissertation entitled “*Differences Between Exporting and Non-Exporting Firms and the Analysis of Export Performance: An Empirical Study in the Olive Oil Sector*” completed in 2005 at the Gebze Institute of Technology, Graduate School of Social Sciences, Department of Business Administration.

1. INTRODUCTION

With globalization, the ability of businesses to achieve sustainable competitive advantage has largely become dependent on their performance in international markets. Export activities not only offer businesses new market opportunities; they also increase capacity utilization rates, strengthen the financial structure by providing foreign exchange earnings, and contribute to the diversification of risk across different markets (Leonidou et al., 2002). Therefore, measuring export performance with an accurate and multi-dimensional approach is of strategic importance for both business managers and policymakers.

The literature shows that numerous variables and measurement approaches are used to measure export performance. This situation reveals different dimensions of the concept, but also leads to conceptual confusion regarding measurement. In the literature, the indicators used in measuring export performance are generally classified into three groups: financial, non-financial, and mixed measures (Zou & Stan, 1998). However, it is noteworthy that the most commonly used financial indicators in practice are sales-based measures such as export sales volume, export intensity, and export growth rate (Zou et al., 1998).

While sales-based indicators reveal the size of a company's presence in foreign markets and its market expansion success, they are insufficient to explain the contribution of exports to the company's profitability, cash flow, and financial sustainability. Export activities, however, entail financial consequences such as long collection periods, high working capital requirements, exchange rate risk, and the need for external financing; thus, they directly affect not only the company's revenue structure but also its liquidity level, capital structure, and value creation capacity. This situation demonstrates that evaluating export performance solely based on sales volume indicators does not reflect the true nature of that performance.

When theoretical studies on export performance are examined, it is seen that the determinants of performance are considered within the framework of firm characteristics, management structure, strategy, environmental factors, and organizational competencies (Aaby & Slater, 1989; Cavusgil & Zou, 1994). However, it is noteworthy that studies focusing on the systematic consideration of accounting-based financial indicators within an integrated model for measuring performance are limited. Yet, accounting-based performance measurement tools provide objective and comparable information regarding a company's value creation capacity, allowing for a holistic analysis of the financial results of exports.

In international marketing literature, export performance has mostly been evaluated through market-based outputs, while in accounting and finance literature, business performance has been analyzed through financial ratios and value-based metrics. The fact that these two approaches have largely developed independently makes it difficult to comprehensively reveal the true impact of export activities on business value. Considering that export performance is a multi-dimensional construct encompassing both market success and financial value creation capacity, there is a need for a performance measurement framework that integrates marketing and accounting disciplines.

Based on this premise, the main objective of this study is to theoretically identify accounting-based financial indicators that can be used to measure export performance and to propose an integrated measurement model that evaluates the contribution of exports to a company's financial success within the framework of sales, profitability, and cash flow dimensions. Accordingly, the study argues that export performance should be considered not only in terms of size and growth indicators, but also in conjunction with financial sustainability and value creation capacity.

This study is expected to make three main contributions to the literature. First, it offers a multidimensional evaluation framework based on accounting-based financial indicators, moving beyond the commonly used one-dimensional approaches in measuring export performance. Second, it proposes a composite performance index that allows for a holistic analysis of the financial consequences of export performance. Third, the developed model aims to provide a testable measurement tool for future empirical studies.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE

Export performance is one of the key indicators determining the success level of businesses in the process of entering international markets. Export performance expresses the degree to which a business achieves its economic and strategic goals in international markets (Cavusgil & Zou, 1994). In the literature, the determinants of export performance have been examined within the framework of numerous variables such as firm characteristics, management structure, strategy, environmental factors, and organizational culture (Aaby & Slater, 1989; Cavusgil & Zou, 1994). In the literature, the indicators used in measuring performance are grouped into three categories: financial, strategic, and perceptual (Richard et al., 2009). The Export Performance Scale (EXPERF) developed by Zou et al. (1998) revealed that export performance consists of financial, strategic, and satisfaction dimensions. However, it is observed that accounting-based ratios are not systematically considered in the measurement of the financial dimension.

A review of the literature on measuring export performance reveals several prominent theoretical approaches. These approaches are generally grouped into four main categories: sales-based indicators, strategic/market-based metrics, managerial perception-based assessments, and financial performance indicators. Sales-based metrics highlight the volumetric dimension of exports, while strategic indicators focus on the company's competitiveness in foreign markets. Perceptual metrics reflect managers' evaluations of export activities, and financial indicators allow for the analysis of the impact of exports on the company's profitability. However, each of these approaches reflects only a specific dimension of export performance and, when used alone, does not allow for a holistic assessment. This highlights the need for integrated measurement models that consider the multi-dimensional nature of export performance. The main approaches to measuring export performance and their fundamental limitations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Approaches to Measuring Export Performance

Measurement Approach	Indicators	Main Limitation
Sales-based	Export sales, export intensity	Does not reflect profitability
Strategic	Market share, entry into new markets	Does not indicate financial sustainability
Perceptual	Managerial satisfaction	Lacks objectivity
Financial	Profitability ratios	Insufficient when used alone

Source: Zou et al. (1998); Cavusgil & Zou (1994)

While these approaches highlight the multifaceted nature of export performance, they have not sufficiently focused on integrating the financial indicators used in measuring performance into a unified model. Export performance should be evaluated not only by the level of export sales but also by the degree to which the company achieves its strategic and economic objectives. Exports are directly related to the company's goals of growth, profitability, and competitiveness (Cavusgil & Zou, 1994). However, it is observed that most indicators used in measuring export performance are based on sales volume (Zou et al., 1998). Yet, export activities directly affect the company's profitability structure, working capital needs, and cash flow cycle. This situation necessitates the evaluation of export performance through accounting-based financial indicators.

Accounting-based performance measurement is one of the most important and objective evaluation tools for revealing the extent to which a business creates value as a result of its activities. Data obtained through financial statements allow for the analysis not only of changes in sales volume but also of the contribution of these sales to profitability, cash flow, and financial sustainability. In this respect, accounting-based performance indicators play a critical role in evaluating the relationship between business strategies and performance results (Chenhall, 2003; Richard et al., 2009). Considering the impact of export activities on the financial structure of the business, profitability indicators are among the key measures that reveal the capacity of these activities to generate economic value. Ratios such as gross profit margin, return on assets (ROA), and return on equity (ROE) allow for the analysis of the value creation process by showing not only the revenue-generating power of exports but also the extent to which business assets and equity are used effectively (Hitt et al., 2020; Kieso et al., 2020).

Since export activities often place significant pressure on liquidity due to long collection periods and high working capital requirements, liquidity indicators such as the current ratio and acid-test ratio are critical

in assessing the ability to meet short-term liabilities. Studies examining the relationship between liquidity level and firm performance show that businesses with sufficient liquidity are more resilient to uncertainties in foreign markets and can manage financing costs more effectively (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 2017; García-Teruel & Martínez-Solano, 2007). Furthermore, the operational efficiency of exports can be analyzed through operational efficiency indicators. Ratios such as accounts receivable turnover and inventory turnover reveal the extent to which a company's sales in international markets are supported by collection and inventory management processes, thus allowing for an assessment of the contribution of exports to operational efficiency (Penman, 2013).

One of the most important integrated indicators in analyzing the financial sustainability of export activities is the cash conversion cycle. Calculated by considering inventory holding period, accounts receivable collection period, and accounts payable payment period together, the cash conversion cycle shows how long it takes for a business to recover the cash it generates from its operations and reveals the effectiveness of working capital management. A shorter cash conversion cycle indicates that the business can operate with lower financing needs, while a longer cash conversion cycle increases liquidity risk and raises dependence on external financing (Deloof, 2003; Shin & Soenen, 1998). This situation becomes even more pronounced for exporting businesses, as the length of delivery and collection periods in international trade makes working capital management one of the determining factors of performance.

Financial structure indicators contribute to the assessment of the risk dimension of performance by revealing the sources from which exports are financed. The debt ratio and financial leverage level show the financial risks that may arise when exports are financed with foreign sources and shed light on the relationship between capital structure and performance (Titman et al., 2018). However, beyond traditional accounting-based performance metrics, value-based performance indicators allow for the evaluation of the impact of export activities on the long-term firm value. Economic Value Added (EVA) reveals the true value creation by measuring whether the firm generates a return above its cost of capital, while the market value/book value ratio reflects investors' expectations regarding the firm's future performance (Stewart, 1991; Young & O'Byrne, 2001). In this respect, accounting-based performance indicators offer a holistic analytical framework that allows for the evaluation of export performance not only in terms of sales volume but also in terms of profitability, cash generation capacity, financial risk, and long-term value creation capacity.

In addition to traditional financial ratios, Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) methods, which allow performance dimensions to be evaluated with different weights, are widely used in measuring financial performance through composite indices. In this context, methods such as Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), Criteria Importance Through Intercriteria Correlation (CRITIC), Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), VlseKriterijumska Optimizacija I Kompromisno Resenje (VIKOR), Entropy, Measurement of Alternatives and Ranking according to Compromise Solution (MARCOS), and Pivot Pairwise Relative Criteria Importance Assessment (PIPRECIA) are frequently preferred in determining criterion weights and ranking alternatives (Saaty, 2008; Diakoulaki et al., 1995; Puška et al., 2020; Đalić et al., 2020; Karakul & Özaydin, 2019). Fuzzy logic-based MCDM approaches, on the other hand, offer a more flexible weighting process by incorporating the uncertain evaluations of decision-makers into the model (Đalić et al., 2020).

The quality of accounting information (especially financial reporting/earnings quality) is a fundamental element determining the extent to which information regarding a company's performance and cash flows is conveyed accurately, timely, and reliably to decision-makers. Comprehensive assessments of the measures, determinants, and consequences of earnings quality show that high-quality reporting reduces information risk and increases the decision-making usefulness of financial statement information (Dechow et al., 2010). Indeed, higher reporting quality increases the effectiveness of investment decisions by reducing frictions such as information asymmetry and agency problems (Biddle et al., 2009), and it is argued that a decrease in reporting quality can increase the cost of capital through the "information risk" channel (Francis et al., 2005). In this context, improving the quality of accounting information can be considered a corporate infrastructure element that can contribute to healthier cash management and resource allocation decisions in activities with high

financing needs and working capital pressures, such as exports. Findings indicating that the likelihood and volume of exports are negatively affected, particularly as the cash conversion cycle lengthens (Mansilla-Fernández & Milgram-Baleix, 2023), suggest that the relationship between working capital management and export performance can also be discussed in the context of financial information quality. Therefore, the reliability of the financial data used in the proposed model is directly related to the quality of accounting information.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN

This study is a conceptual model development research aimed at measuring export performance in an integrated manner through accounting-based financial indicators. The study does not utilize an empirical dataset; instead, it establishes a theoretical framework based on the literature, and demonstrates the computational logic of the proposed model through a hypothetical application. In this respect, the research is both model development and methodological proposal.

The research process consists of four stages. In the first stage, the marketing, international business, accounting, and finance literature on measuring export performance was systematically examined, and the strengths and limitations of existing performance measurement approaches were identified. In the second stage, financial performance indicators in the literature were evaluated, and indicators that could represent export performance from an accounting perspective were determined, creating a three-dimensional structure consisting of sales-based performance, profitability-based performance, and cash flow-based performance.

In the third stage, a composite export performance index based on Z-score standardization was proposed to make the indicators, which are measured in different units, comparable. In this stage, the method for calculating the performance scores for each dimension was presented, and an initial model with equal weighting for each dimension was developed. In the final stage, the applicability of the proposed model was concretized by numerically demonstrating the calculation process of the model using a hypothetical dataset of three companies.

This methodological approach eliminates the limitations arising from measuring export performance based on only a single indicator and allows for the integrated evaluation of different financial dimensions. Furthermore, the proposed model is testable in future empirical studies using different weighting techniques and multi-criteria decision-making methods.

The primary reason for not using an empirical dataset in this study is to develop an integrated model proposal for measuring export performance through accounting-based financial indicators. The focus of the study is not on testing causal relationships between variables, but rather on bringing together performance indicators found in the literature within a systematic framework at a conceptual level. The numerical application created in this context is designed to demonstrate the computational logic of the model and does not constitute an empirical finding.

4. PROPOSED MODEL: INTEGRATED EXPORT PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT MODEL

Accurate and holistic evaluation of export performance requires moving beyond traditional metrics based solely on sales volume. Export activities are a multi-dimensional process that directly affects a company's revenue structure, profitability, working capital requirements, and cash flow cycle. Therefore, measuring export performance should utilize accounting-based data provided by financial statements and address performance through a multi-dimensional approach.

4.1. Model Dimensions

This study proposes evaluating export performance within the framework of three key financial dimensions:

1. Sales-based performance
2. Profitability-based performance

3. Cash flow-based performance

When these three dimensions are considered together, the true contribution of exports to a company's financial success can be revealed.

4.1.1. Sales-Based Export Performance

Sales-based indicators are the most fundamental metrics revealing a company's presence in international markets and its success in market expansion. These indicators show the scale of exports, their growth trend, and their place within total operations.

Key indicators that can be used in this context include:

- Share of export sales in total sales (export intensity),
- Export sales volume,
- Export sales growth rate,
- Trend of increasing exports within total sales.

Sales-based performance indicators reveal a company's success in entering foreign markets and its level of market diversification, but they are insufficient to explain the financial effectiveness of exports alone. Therefore, sales performance should be evaluated in conjunction with profitability and cash flow dimensions.

4.1.2. Profitability-Based Export Performance

The most critical factor for the sustainability of export activities is the profit these activities generate for the business. Export activities carried out with high sales volume, but low profitability can weaken the financial structure of the business. Therefore, it is essential to use profitability-based indicators in evaluating export performance.

The main indicators that can be used at this level are as follows:

- Gross profit margin
- Operating profit margin
- Net profit margin
- Return on assets (ROA)
- Return on equity (ROE)

These indicators reveal the extent to which exports contribute to the overall financial performance of the business. Measuring profitability-based performance allows for an assessment of whether exports are not only a means of growth but also a tool for value creation.

4.1.3. Cash Flow Based Export Performance

Export activities often place significant pressure on a company's cash cycle due to long collection periods and high working capital requirements. Therefore, cash flow-based indicators should be considered when evaluating export performance.

Key indicators that can be used in this context include:

- Cash conversion cycle,
- Accounts receivable collection period,
- Inventory holding period,
- Trade payable period,
- Cash flow/sales from operations.

Short cash conversion cycles indicate that export activities are carried out with a lower financing burden, reducing the company's liquidity risk. This is a critical indicator for the financial sustainability of export performance.

4.2. Evaluation Logic of the Integrated Model

In the proposed model, export performance is measured not by a single indicator, but by evaluating three dimensions together. This approach allows for the simultaneous analysis of exports':

- market penetration (sales dimension),
- value provided to the business (profitability dimension),
- financial sustainability (cash flow dimension).

In this context, a business with high export performance is expected to have:

- a high share of export sales,
- a strong level of profitability,
- a short cash conversion cycle.

Due to the multifaceted nature of export performance, it is necessary to convert different financial indicators into a single performance score. However, since these indicators have different units of measurement (rate, percentage, day, etc.), they are not directly comparable. Therefore, this study proposes a two-stage method for calculating the composite index. In the first stage, the variables are standardized, and in the second stage, the dimensional and overall performance scores are calculated.

4.3. Method of Calculating the Index

4.3.1. Standardization of Indicators

A Z-score transformation is applied to each financial indicator:

$$Z_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij} - \bar{X}_j}{S_j}$$

As a result of this transformation, all variables are brought to a common scale with a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. This makes indicators with different units of measurement comparable.

For indicators where a low value is desirable, such as cash conversion cycle and accounts receivable collection cycle, the sign of the resulting Z-value is reversed to align with the performance aspect.

4.3.2. Calculating Dimensional Scores

Each performance dimension (sales, profitability, and cash flow) may consist of multiple indicators. Therefore, the dimension score is obtained by taking the arithmetic mean of the Z-scores for the relevant dimension.

$$\text{Dimension Score} = \frac{\sum Z_{\text{indicators}}}{\text{Number of indicators}} = \frac{\sum Z_i}{n}$$

This process is done separately for each dimension:

- Sales performance score
- Profitability performance score
- Cash flow performance score

The values obtained at this stage represent the standardized dimension performance.

4.3.3. Calculation of the Composite Export Performance Index (EPI)

The overall export performance score is calculated by taking the equally weighted arithmetic mean of three key dimensions:

$$EPI = \frac{\text{Sales Performance Score} + \text{Profitability Performance Score} + \text{Cash Flow Performance Score}}{3}$$

In this approach, equal weighting was chosen as the initial model because there is no empirical evidence regarding the relative importance of the dimensions. However, in future empirical studies, the relative importance of the dimensions can be determined using different weighting methods (entropy, AHP, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), etc.).

Measuring export performance holistically requires bringing together indicators representing different financial dimensions within a systematic framework. The composite export performance index proposed in this study is based on a three-dimensional structure that evaluates the impact of export activities on the business not only in terms of sales volume but also in terms of profitability and cash generation capacity. The sales-based performance dimension reveals the contribution of exports to the company's growth and expansion in foreign markets; the profitability-based performance dimension measures the impact of export activities on production, operations, and overall financial success. The cash flow-based performance dimension allows for the analysis of the consequences of exports on the company's financing needs, working capital efficiency, and the cash conversion power of sales. In this context, a measurement matrix was created for each indicator by determining the calculation method, the expected direction of performance, and the financial meaning it represents. Thus, a standardized structure was established that allows indicators with different units of measurement to be evaluated within the same analytical framework. The dimensions, indicators, and calculation methods used in the proposed composite export performance index are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Export Performance Composite Index Measurement Matrix

Dimension	Indicator	Calculation	Expected Direction	Description
Sales-Based Performance	Export Intensity	Export Sales / Net Sales	+	Indicates the share of exports in total operations
	Export Sales Growth	$(\text{Export}_t - \text{Export}_{t-1}) / \text{Export}_{t-1}$	+	Measures expansion in foreign markets
	Contribution of Exports to Total Sales Growth	Export Growth / Total Sales Growth	+	Indicates whether growth is export-driven
Profitability-Based Performance	Gross Profit Margin	Gross Profit / Net Sales	+	Reflects the effect of exports on production profitability
	Operating Profit Margin	Operating Profit / Net Sales	+	Indicates operational efficiency
	Net Profit Margin	Net Profit / Net Sales	+	Reflects overall financial success
	Return on Assets (ROA)	Net Profit / Total Assets	+	Indicates efficiency in asset utilization
	Return on Equity (ROE)	Net Profit / Equity	+	Reflects return to shareholders
Cash Flow-Based Performance	Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC)	Inventory Days + Receivables Days - Payables Days	-	Indicates financing requirement
	Receivables Collection Period	$365 / \text{Receivables Turnover}$	-	Reflects export collection efficiency
	Operating Cash Flow Ratio	Operating Cash Flow / Net Sales	+	Indicates the ability of sales to generate cash
	Working Capital Turnover	Net Sales / Net Working Capital	+	Reflects efficiency in working capital utilization

The proposed composite index:

- Reflects the multidimensional nature of export performance

- Enables inter-firm comparisons
- Suitable for time series analysis
- Can be used in panel data studies
- Reduces deviations resulting from univariate measurement.

In this respect, it offers an integrated, accounting-based performance measurement tool for both academic studies and practitioners.

An examination of approaches to measuring export performance in the literature reveals that existing measurement methods focus on a specific dimension of performance and are therefore insufficient for a holistic assessment. In particular, sales-based indicators, while revealing the volumetric size of exports, do not consider elements that determine financial sustainability, such as profitability and cash flow. Similarly, assessments based solely on financial ratios offer limited information about export growth dynamics and expansion performance in foreign markets. This situation highlights the need for measurement models that consider the multi-dimensional nature of export performance and combine different financial indicators within a common analytical framework.

The composite export performance model proposed in this study aims to overcome the limitations of traditional approaches and evaluates export performance within an integrated framework that considers sales, profitability, and cash flow dimensions together. Furthermore, the model enables the creation of an index that allows for inter-company and inter-period comparisons by standardizing financial indicators with different units of measurement. Thus, it becomes possible to analyze export performance not only in terms of size but also in terms of financial sustainability and value creation capacity. The key differences between the proposed model and traditional measurement approaches are presented comparatively in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of Traditional and Proposed Export Performance Models.

Criterion	Traditional Measurement	Proposed Model
Multidimensionality	Not available	Available
Financial sustainability	Not measured	Measured
Comparability	Low	High
Index construction	Not available	Available

4.4. Steps in Calculating the Export Performance Index: A Quantitative Application

The calculation process for the proposed composite export performance index consists of three stages. This process includes converting financial indicators with different units of measurement into a common scale, obtaining performance scores on a dimension basis, and calculating the final performance index.

To provide a concrete and measurable demonstration of the calculation process for the proposed composite export performance index, a hypothetical dataset consisting of three companies was created. This dataset was designed to show step-by-step how the indicators representing the sales-based, profitability-based, and cash flow-based performance dimensions included in the model were standardized and how the composite index value was obtained. Accordingly, export intensity was determined as the key indicator representing sales-based performance, return on assets (ROA) as the key indicator representing profitability-based performance, and cash conversion cycle as the key indicator representing cash flow-based performance. By presenting the raw financial data and the mean and standard deviation values to be used in Z-score standardization for each company, a methodological basis was established for making indicators with different units of measurement comparable and for calculating the composite export performance index. The sample dataset and descriptive statistics for the calculation of the export performance index are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Sample Data Set and Descriptive Statistics for Export Performance Index Calculation

Firm	Export Intensity	ROA	Cash Conversion Cycle (days)
A	0.400	0.120	90
B	0.250	0.080	120
C	0.150	0.050	150
Mean	0.267	0.083	120
Standard Deviation	0.126	0.035	30

The average for each financial indicator is calculated as follows: $\bar{x} = (\sum Xi / n)$

For example, the average of the export intensity indicators was calculated as follows:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{0,400 + 0,250 + 0,150}{3} = 0,267$$

Averages are calculated in the same way for other financial indicators as well.

Using the descriptive statistics (Mean–Standard Deviation) given in Table 4, Z-scores were calculated for each business as follows. In this example, the sales dimension is represented by export intensity, the profitability dimension by ROA, and the cash flow dimension by cash conversion cycle (CCC). Since a low CCC is a desirable indicator, the sign of the calculated Z-score was reversed to align with the performance aspect.

✓ **Z-Scores for Business A:**

- Sales (Export Intensity) → $Z = \frac{0,400 - 0,267}{0,126} = \frac{0,133}{0,126} = 1,056$
- Profitability (ROA) → $Z = \frac{0,120 - 0,083}{0,035} = \frac{0,037}{0,035} = 1,057$
- Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) → $Z = \frac{90 - 120}{30} = -1,000$
 $Z^* = 1,000$

* The sign of the Z value has been reversed.

Z-scores are calculated similarly for other businesses as well. Each dimension may consist of more than one indicator. In this case, the arithmetic mean of the Z-scores for the relevant dimension is taken. For example, if the sales dimension consisted of two indicators (export intensity and export growth rate), the average of the Z-scores of both indicators would constitute the Z-score for the sales dimension.

Z-score standardization was applied to make the indicators comparable using the raw data presented in Table 4. This transformation transferred each variable to a common scale with a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. This made it possible to evaluate financial indicators with different units of measurement within the same analytical framework. For indicators where a low value is desired, such as cash conversion cycle (CCC) and accounts receivable collection cycle, the sign of the obtained Z-scores was reversed to accurately reflect the direction of performance. As a result of this process, all indicators were standardized so that higher values indicate better performance. The standardized performance scores of the companies are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Calculated Z-Scores for the Sample Data Set

Firm	Sales Z-Score	Profitability Z-Score	Cash Flow Z-Score*
A	1.056	1.057	1.000
B	-0.135	-0.086	0.000
C	-0.929	-0.943	-1.000

* The sign of the Z-score is reversed.

Table 5 shows that as a result of the standardization process, each indicator has become comparable. Accordingly, it is understood that company A has the highest performance value in terms of export intensity and return on assets, while company C is below average in both indicators. For the cash conversion cycle, since a shorter cycle indicates higher performance, the Z-scores were reversed. The results show that Company A has the highest performance in this dimension as well. The values obtained at this stage serve as the basis for calculating the dimension-based performance scores and for constructing the composite export performance index.

The overall performance score is calculated by taking the arithmetic mean of the three dimensions. Using a hypothetical dataset of three companies, the Combined Export Performance Index (EPI) will be calculated as follows:

$$EPI = \frac{\text{Sales Performance Score} + \text{Profitability Performance Score} + \text{Cash Flow Performance Score}}{3}$$

Firm A → $EPI = \frac{1.056 + 1.057 + 1.000}{3} = 1.038$

Firm B → $EPI = \frac{-0.135 - 0.086 + 0.000}{3} = -0.074$

Firm C → $EPI = \frac{-0.929 - 0.943 - 1.000}{3} = -0.957$

Using standardized indicators, scores were obtained for each company regarding sales-based performance, profitability-based performance, and cash flow-based performance dimensions. In this study, equal weights were assumed for the dimensions in the initial model, and the composite export performance index was calculated as the arithmetic mean of the performance scores of the three dimensions. Thus, export performance was evaluated within a multidimensional framework without relying on a single financial indicator. The composite export performance index values for the companies are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Composite Export Performance Index (EPI) Scores

Firm	EPI
A	1,038
B	-0,074
C	-0,957

According to the composite export performance index results presented in Table 6, company A has the highest performance value. This company's above-average performance in sales-based, profitability-based, and cash flow-based indicators resulted in a high integrated index value. Company B performed close to average, while company C had the lowest index value as it performed below average in all dimensions. These findings indicate that evaluating export performance solely based on sales volume can be misleading; considering profitability and cash flow dimensions together provides a more realistic performance assessment. The proposed composite index allows monitoring the multifaceted impact of export activities on a company's financial structure through a single performance indicator.

This approach makes it possible to identify export activities that, despite having high export volumes, are not financially sustainable due to low profitability or long cash conversion cycles. Therefore, the proposed index offers an integrated performance measurement tool that allows for the analysis of the financial consequences of export performance within a multi-dimensional framework.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that the sales-based, one-dimensional approaches commonly used in the literature for measuring export performance are insufficient in explaining the financial success of a business. It proposes an accounting-based measurement model that allows for a holistic evaluation of the financial results of exports. The main finding of the study is that export performance should be evaluated not only in terms of the level or growth rate of export sales, but also in terms of the contribution of these activities to the company's profitability, cash generation capacity, and financial sustainability. The model developed in this context considers export performance within an integrated structure of three fundamental financial dimensions: sales-based performance, profitability-based performance, and cash flow-based performance.

The theoretical contribution of this study is to bring together the market-based output approach, which dominates the marketing literature in evaluating export performance, and the value-based performance measurement approach found in the accounting and finance literature, within the same analytical framework. In this respect, the study offers an interdisciplinary performance measurement perspective that allows for the correlation of export performance with firm value. This approach, which demonstrates that export performance should be considered not only in terms of market outputs but also in conjunction with the firm's value creation capacity, provides a conceptual integration between the international marketing literature and the accounting-based performance measurement understanding.

Methodologically, the study presents a systematic framework for measuring export performance using financial statement data and demonstrates that financial indicators of different scales can be standardized and transformed into a single comparable performance score. This approach provides a measurement infrastructure suitable for inter-firm comparisons, monitoring performance changes over time, and panel data analysis. In this respect, the proposed model serves as a testable and improvable analytical tool for future empirical research.

The practical contribution of this study is that it offers business managers the opportunity to evaluate their export strategies not only in terms of sales increase targets, but also within a holistic performance framework that centers on financial sustainability. Thanks to the proposed model, it will be possible to identify export activities that generate high sales volume but fail to generate profitability or negatively impact cash flow at an early stage, and to make more rational resource allocation decisions. Furthermore, the multi-dimensional performance approach offered by the model can contribute to policymakers developing more robust performance indicators for evaluating the quality of exports.

However, since this study is a conceptual model proposal, it has not been tested with empirical data. Future studies can test the validity of the proposed performance index, determine the relative weights of the dimensions, and compare alternative weighting methods through applications on different sectors and country samples. In addition, including variables such as accounting information quality, exchange rate risk management, and financing structure in the model will contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of the financial determinants of export performance.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the need to move beyond the traditional sales volume-based approach to evaluating export performance and proposes an integrated measurement framework that considers exports in conjunction with the company's profitability, cash flow, and financial sustainability dimensions. In this respect, the study contributes conceptually to the academic literature and develops a more realistic and sustainable performance evaluation perspective for practitioners.

This study aims to develop a conceptual model and has not been tested with an empirical dataset. This prevents a comparative evaluation of the proposed composite export performance index across different sectors, country groups, and firm sizes. Furthermore, the dimensions included in the model are treated with equal weighting, and no weighting analysis has been conducted to determine the relative importance of the dimensions. In future studies, dimension weights can be determined using Multi-Criteria Decision Making methods or statistical techniques, and the model can be tested on empirical datasets.

However, although the financial indicators used in this study were selected from generally accepted accounting-based performance metrics, sector-specific performance dynamics may differ. Therefore, in future research, it is possible to adapt the model by creating different sets of indicators on a sectoral basis. In addition, the explanatory power of the model can be increased by examining the dynamic structure of export performance through panel data and time series analyses.

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